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[The effect of Activin pathway modulation on the expression of both pluripotency and differentiation markers during early zebrafish development compared with other vertebrates](#)

Activin-like factors control many developmental processes, including pluripotency maintenance and differentiation. Although Activin-like factors' action in mesendoderm induction has been demonstrated in zebrafish, their involvement in preserving the stemness remains unknown. To investigate the role of maternal Activin-like factors, their effects were promoted or blocked using synthetic human Activin A or SB-431542 treatments respectively until the maternal to zygotic transition. To study the role of zygotic Activin-like factors, SB-431542 treatment was also applied after the maternal to zygotic transition. The effect of the pharmacological modulations of the Activin/Smad pathway was then studied on the mRNA expressions of the *ndr1*, *ndr2*, *tbxta* (no tail/*ntl*) as the differentiation index, *mych*, *nanog*, and *oct4* (*pou5f3*) as the pluripotency markers of the zebrafish embryonic cells as well as *sox17* as a definitive endoderm marker. Expression of the target genes was measured at the 16-cell, 256-cell, 1K-cell, oblong, dome, and shield stages using the real-time quantitative polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR). Activation of the maternal Activin signaling pathway led to an increase in zygotic expression of the *tbxta*, particularly marked at the oblong stage. In other words, promotion of the maternal Activin/Smad pathway induced differentiation by advancing the major peaks of *ndr1* and *nanog*, thereby eliciting *tbxta* expression. Whereas suppression of the maternal or zygotic Activin/Smad pathway sustained the pluripotency by preventing the major peaks of *ndr1* and *nanog* as well as *tbxta* encoding.

Keywords: activin-like factors, differentiation, pluripotency, zebrafish

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